

The Religious Society of Friends

also known as “Quakers, Quakerism”

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Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Liberal Religion, Post-Christian, American Christianity, Religious Group

The Religious Society of Friends (Quakers) The Religious Society of Friends, better known by the once derogatory and later reclaimed moniker “Quakers,” are a historically Christian group. One of many small religious sects to emerge in the wake of the English Civil War, the Quakers formed under the inspiration of the teachings of George Fox, a weaver turned preacher who elevated the “priesthood of the believer” to a hitherto unseen extreme. Fox argued for the abolition of the priesthood (or the laity, as Friends might say), in favor of a Christian community modeled on Fox’s understanding of the early church, one in which all were called to ministry and equally able to communicate with a divine “Light Within.” Fox and the early Friends seem to have been a premillenarian sect who felt Christ’s return was immanent and prepared accordingly, but by the 1670s the Friends had begun to internalize the second coming and institutionalize in earnest. Friends became notorious throughout England for the uniqueness of their theological and social practices—worshipping in silence, eschewing paid ministers and tithes, refusing to use the “pagan” names of months and days, adopting plain clothes and the informal “thou” in place of the honorific “you,” refusing to doff hats for anyone but the Lord, and, most importantly, their refusal to swear oaths in courts of law (after Matthew 5:34) which led to their frequent imprisonment. Even after the Friends were granted formal toleration in the Toleration Act of 1689, a number chose to immigrate to the New World, driven by economic and religious motivations. Though Friends began arriving in the Americas as early as 1655, they founded their most influential settlement in Pennsylvania (awarded as a charter to Quaker William Penn in 1681 to repay a lien owed his father), where Friends remained the dominant force in the legislature until 1756, when they resigned en masse rather than dedicate taxes for the French and Indian War, objecting on pacifist grounds. Though never a numerically significant portion of the American population, Friends assumed outsized importance in American religious history by spearheading a variety of social movements: The American abolition movement, women’s suffrage, Native American rights, and pacifist movements all have Quaker origins and inspirations. A series of schisms split the American Quakers in the nineteenth century, following the trajectory of many Protestant denominations at the time. The most significant was the 1827 Orthodox-Hicksite split, the Hicksites rallying around the teachings of Elias Hicks, who taught that Jesus became Christ but was not born divine, and that any modern Friend who might follow Jesus’ example in discerning the will of the Inward Light within all. For Hicks, the Bible was valuable as one source among many attesting to God’s previous revelations but was not the unique word of God and should be subordinated to reason and experience. Orthodox Friends, by contrast, affirmed the traditional Christian beliefs that Christ was the sole Son of God who was sent to earth to redeem humanity by dying on the cross. Orthodox Friends increasingly integrated with other Protestant denominations in both theology and practice, while Hicksite Friends grew closer with other progressive denominations active in social movements. The split foreran the two most important Quaker bodies today, the liberal Friends General Conference (FGC) and evangelical Friends United Meeting (FUM). FGC Friends have maintained the distinctively quiet (“unprogrammed”) style of Quaker worship but are arguably post-Christian, while FUM meetings are effectively Protestant. The two groups share little with one another except competing claims to a shared spiritual lineage and the Quaker name itself. The Quakers were not historically known for missions after their initial proselytization efforts in the seventeenth century, but a series of successful international missions initiated in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries have led to large Quaker communities in Kenya, Burundi, Guatemala, and Bolivia. These international meetings are typically, though not invariably, affiliated with either the Evangelical Friends or the Friends United Meeting, and so

more closely resemble other Protestant Christian churches than the more liberal FGC Friends. Over a third of the world's Quakers live in Kenya, the likely provenance of the next stage of Quaker history.

Date Range: 1652 CE - 2020 CE

Region: The Religious Society of Friends (Quakers)

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Kenya, United States, England, Pennsylvania

The Quakers were founded in England, primarily in Lancashire County, but reached the height of their social and political influence in America, after the grant of Pennsylvania to William Penn. Today over a third of Quakers live in Kenya, with sizable meetings also located in Burundi, Guatemala, and Bolivia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Angell, Stephen Ward, ed. 2015. *The Oxford handbook of Quaker studies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Source 2: Dandelion, Pink. 2010. *An introduction to Quakerism*. Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Source 3: Hamm, Thomas D. 1992. *The transformation of American Quakerism: Orthodox Friends, 1800-1907*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/quakerstudies/>
- Source 1 Description: Journal of the Quaker Studies Research Association (QSRA) and the Centre for Postgraduate Quaker Studies, Woodbrooke Quaker Study Centre. Vols. 1-14 (2010) available to all, Vols. 15 - present subscribers only.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Sy2Su2xI98>
- Source 2 Description: Especially concise video of Max Carter, Professor of Quaker Studies at Guilford College, discussing the socio-theological origins of the Friends
- Source 3 URL: <https://quakerinfo.org/index>
- Source 3 Description: The homepage of the Quaker Information Center, associated with the Earlham School of Religion

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/43031/43031-h/43031-h.htm>
- Source 1 Description: An open-access version of Rufus Jones' edition of George Fox's Journal
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.qhpress.org/texts/barclay/apology/>
- Source 2 Description: Robert Barclay's *Apology* (1676), the first systematic theological treatise published

by a Friend. Includes an editorial introduction and a glossary of archaic terms.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ccel.org/ccel/w/woolman/journal/cache/journal.pdf>

– Source 3 Description: The Journal of John Woolman, a foundational text for both Friends and the American abolitionist movement

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Friends were one of many radical Christian sects to emerge in the aftermath of the English Civil War. In the seventeenth century Quakers often interacted involuntarily with the Anglican establishment in England. Friends were originally persecuted in both England and the early American colonies. (For instance, Massachusetts passed a law saying that Friends would be executed if they continued to preach after having already been twice banned; Mary Dyer and three other Friends were hung under the provision.) In the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries Friends encountered the full range of religious diversity in America. Professor of Quakerism Max Carter discusses a common question in *Quaker Studies: Were the Quakers Puritan?* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ok9b-IYjoI8>

Reference: Barbour, Hugh. *The Quakers in Puritan England*. New Haven and London: Friends United Press, 1985.

Reference: Reay, B.. *The Quakers in the English Revolution*. London: Temple Smith, 1985.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Friends were one of a number of small religious sects who formed in the wake of post-reformation and -restoration England in the mid-seventeenth century and all were competing for converts. The "other religious groups" here references only other Christian denominations.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Friends were among the first to establish formal religious toleration in Pennsylvania and in general believed that if left to their own devices all people would see the truth of Quakerism and convert. Quakers consequently believed there was no sense in forcing or coercing conversion to Quakerism. Following the eighteenth century schisms, many Gurneyite Friends adopted the evangelical view that Christianity was the only "true" religion and that Christ-language and beliefs were required for divine experience. Hicksite Friends emphasized the universality of the early Friends and believed that Christianity was only mode of describing a shared experience of the divine.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Quakers were pacifist and strove never to act violently, but they were persecuted in large numbers, particularly in the 1650s and 1660s, culminating in the Quaker Act of 1662, which required subjects to swear an oath to the king. Since Quakers did not swear oaths based on their reading of Matthew 5:34, the Act was drafted specifically to target and imprison Quakers. During the Quietist Period (1692-1805), Friends became increasingly established and were less often in direct contact with other governmental or religious forces. However, Friends would face periodic persecution for refusing to fight in the Civil War or either of the World Wars.

Reference: Brock, Peter. *The Quaker Peace Testimony 1660 to 1914*. York, England; Syracuse, N.Y.: Sessions Book Trust; North American distributors, Syracuse University Press, 1990.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Quaker_Peace_Testimony_1660_to_1914.html?hl=&id=hBxjQgAACAAJ.

Reference: Horle, C. W.. *The Quakers and the English Legal System, 1660-1688*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1988.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: Since most conflict was with local governments, Friends rarely encountered violence elsewhere.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout the seventeenth century, there was some confusion over who was a Quaker due to people claiming the moniker hoping to receive the care of local meetings and the financial benefits they conferred. In 1668 Fox directed all meetings to keep proper record books (though there is evidence that many already were), which led to extensive record keeping in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, including membership roles. Both joining and leaving the Society became relatively formalized processes.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Individual Friends meetings formalized the practice of birthright membership throughout the eighteenth century, beginning with London Yearly Meeting in 1737. If one parent was disowned, or kicked out of the Society, the child would not have birthright membership. However, one could still become a Friend even without such a birthright.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, and even birthright Friends were expected to have their own experience of conviction of Quaker truth. In more recent years the Quaker membership process has come to resemble that of other Protestant churches. Even in the past one could be disowned

(excommunicated) by one's meeting or join the Society voluntarily if willing to live under its social strictures.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Friends were one of the first Christian groups to argue for the full spiritual equality of women, drawing the ire of the seventeenth-century Christian establishment in the process. Women wouldn't receive equal political representation in the Society for some time.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: In its formative years in the 1650s and 1660s, proselytizing and preaching widely across England were considered indispensable functions of the Society. The most famous early Friends were perhaps the "Valiant Sixty," a group of itinerant Friends who preached across England. The wide traveling of the Quakers at a time when the average Englishman spent their lives within a ten mile radius was one reason they were viewed with suspicion. In Quakerism's later Quietist period, beginning in the eighteenth century, Friends increasingly turned inward and stopped recruiting so actively. However, in the late nineteenth century, Gurneyite Friends of a more evangelical persuasion began sending out missionaries internationally, leading to the large contemporary Quaker communities in Kenya and Bolivia. A 2016 introduction to the distribution of Quakers worldwide: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zn_YqoHOL4M

Reference: Nivonzima, David, and Len Fendall. *Unlocking Horns*. Barclay Press, 2001. https://books.google.com/books/about/Unlocking_Horns.html?hl=&id=ztDX4lp-sw8C.

Reference: Rasmussen, A. M. B.. *A History of the Quaker Movement in Africa*. London: British Academic Press, 1995.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: In many contemporary FGC circles one would even be encouraged not to proselytize out

of respect for the religious persuasion of the other person. Even during Quakerism's more conventionally Christian period, Friends adopted a quietist orientation and hoped to witness through their manner of living rather than direct conversion.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Indeed, until the late nineteenth century, there were no religious professionals, as the Friends rejected a hireling ministry.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: One might make a case that the late nineteenth and early twentieth century missions were coercive in the same way that all missions linked to the colonialist apparatus for the British and American states are, but they were neither more nor less coercive than other Protestant missions.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The only time the Friends were directly in control of their politics was when they ran the General Assembly of Pennsylvania from approximately 1681-1756 when the Quakers resigned rather than dedicate taxes for the French-Indian War.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Apostasy" is perhaps not quite the right word for a group that eschews creeds, though in the past Friends could be "disowned" or kicked out of their meeting and stripped of the right to identify as Quaker. This most commonly occurred for marrying someone outside the Society but occasionally for lapses in virtue like sexual immorality or drunkenness. Through the nineteenth century one could be disowned for theological non-conformity (as in the case of the divisions discussed above) but increasingly Friends have adopted a much wider latitude in belief and practice.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: No, not beyond being disowned, and even disowned Friends could continue to participate in many functions of the Society, e.g. meeting for worship.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 100000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.02

Notes: There are more Friends in Kenya than any other country, followed by the U.S., Burundi, Bolivia, and Guatemala. England assumes its outsized importance on the map above for historical rather than numeric reasons.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Recognized" is an interesting term. Friends have historically denied a formal leadership structure even as they embraced concepts like "weighty Friends," "clerks," and others endowed with greater measures of spiritual or bureaucratic responsibility within the meeting organization. In the late nineteenth century "pastoral meetings" emerged as some evangelically-inspired Friends dispensed with the Quaker rejection of a hireling ministry. Today the majority of Quaker meetings are pastoral. The most widely read contemporary Friend is probably preacher and popular theologian Richard Foster. Preacher Philip Gulley's novels have also found a relatively wide audience. Ben Pink Dandelion also bears mentioning as a Friend who has revived the field of Quaker Studies. Foster giving a lecture at George Fox University: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uyONzRRGvQc> Philip Gulley introducing the fictional town of Harmony where his novels are set: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BvxdWkMM0ul> Ben Pink Dandelion's 2014 Swarthmore Lecture: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oRO-IGD9emM> Philip Gulley describing

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Though an extremely loose hierarchy, e.g. individual meetings might have a lead pastor and an associate pastor. It is also worth underscoring that Friends would say the organizational hierarchy is not a reflection of a spiritual hierarchy.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense of a pastor leading a meeting.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among

these leaders:

– No

Notes: Even as local meetings have their own ministers, the meetings themselves are part of larger organizational hierarchies (e.g. the monthly meeting, Friends United Meeting, etc.). Within these groups there is an organizational though not spiritual hierarchy.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Within the larger association of meetings, there might be a clerk or regional coordinator charged with overseeing many local meetings. However, local meetings are free to come and go from the larger hierarchies as they wish (unlike in the Catholic Church for example) and would consider these bodies to be voluntary associations rather than hierarchical.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Because of their belief in the guiding force of the Inward Light (since the Light should be leading everyone), Friends have always sought to make decisions by committee and consensus rather than by top-down models of leadership or majority rule.

Reference: Sheeran, Michael J.. *Beyond Majority Rule*. Philadelphia Yearly Meeting, 1983. https://books.google.com/books/about/Beyond_Majority_Rule.html?hl=&id=r1yvQgAACAAJ.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: Meeting, monthly meeting, yearly meeting, larger association. For any given Quaker meeting there might be no hierarchy at all or even more levels.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Or, only in the sense that they are particularly astute at discerning the leadings of their Light Within, but not in a way qualitatively different from any other Friend.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: See above answer.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that they are recommended for the office on the basis of their abilities in leadership and discernment.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: The individual meeting selects their own ministers, not the larger associative bodies. Hires are made within the larger bodies according to the purview of the relevant committee (e.g. the committee for Peace and Social Concerns might recommend a Peace Coordinator.)

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that one will seek to discern the leadings of the Light Within to inform the selection process.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders can be sanctioned and checked by their meetings or other committees of leaders.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Each Friend is ultimately accountable only to their own Inward Light. The leader can help facilitate the discernment process but cannot unilaterally make pronouncements on another's spiritual state.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Though a historically Christian group, Friends have always downplayed the relative importance of the Bible in favor of the Inward Light, or one's own experience of the divine. The Bible occupied a position of paramount importance in seventeenth-century England. Protestant doctrines like sola scriptura and the priesthood of the believer had become both theologically and socially mainstream. Though early Friends too spoke of the Bible as a testament of God's revelation, they deemphasized its theological importance relative to their contemporaries. Most early Quakers believed that they themselves could commune with the Spirit that inspired the Bible, and that as such the Scriptures were a second-order description of the divine Spirit rather than the Spirit itself, though a particularly valuable one. Fox preached that he received his spiritual revelations directly from Christ, while Barclay wrote in one of the most famous passages in all of Quakerism, “Nevertheless, because the scriptures are only a declaration of the source, and not the source itself, they are not to be considered the principal foundation of all truth and knowledge. They are not even to be considered as the adequate primary rule of all faith and practice. Yet, because they give a true and faithful testimony of the source itself, they are and may be regarded as a secondary rule that is subordinate to the Spirit, from which they obtain all their excellence and certainty.” Barclay's articulation remained the orthodox Quaker position until its fractious nineteenth century, when the rationalist and textual-critical critiques that bifurcated many Protestant denominations split the Quakers as well. For Elias Hicks and the eventual Hicksites, the Bible was clearly subordinate to inward experiences of God in worship; like Barclay, the Hicksites treated scripture as a secondary account of God's word rather than the word itself, and many came to view the Bible as only one account of God's revelation among many, including non- or extra-Christian articulations. Though many of Hicks' Orthodox opponents shared this theological position broadly, they still gave greater primacy to the Bible than did Hicks and objected to its perceived devaluation in Hicksite Quakerism. The two groups would cleave still further in their Biblical understandings. Many Hicksites accepted the rationalist contention that the Bible was best understood as a series of historically-independent manuscripts rather than a unified revelation authored by God. Today, one is as likely to hear a quotation from the Bhagavad Gita or Rumi during an FGC meeting for worship as a Biblical passage. Meanwhile, Orthodox meetings accepted greater and greater evangelical influence, and accordingly began to elevate the Bible in importance, culminating in Joseph John Gurney's contention that Barclay had been wrong to prioritize the Inward Light above the Bible. Contemporary FUM meetings, both in America and internationally, use evangelical language of infallibility and inerrancy to characterize the Bible (though both these doctrines are absent from the 1887 Richmond Declaration). Though not a scripture per se, the Journal of George Fox also bears mentioning as a uniquely important document for Friends.

Reference: Macy, Howard R.. “Quakers and Scripture”. In *The Oxford Handbook of Quaker Studies*, edited by Stephen W. Angell and Pink Dandelion. Oxford University Press, 2013.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible.

Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Though not a unique one, as at present more conservative Friends accept the broader Protestant notion that the Bible is divinely-inspired and infallible, while FGC Friends would accept a historical-critical account in which the books were authored separately across many different time periods. In this sense, the “origin” of the Bible among early Friends might simply refer to the idea that a group of people who were divinely inspired bore witness to their experience, but that there was no Spirit actively guiding their actions or words.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Some Orthodox Friends and most Gurneyites would agree that the Bible was divinely revealed. However, Hicksite Friends would merely say that it was inspired. Where the earliest Friends fall on this spectrum has been a matter of considerable debate.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Hicksite Friends and contemporary FGC members argue that the scriptures are inspired by God but not his direct revelation. In this sense there are numerous possible scriptures.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: "Semi-divine" is an interesting category for Friends. One might say that someone writing in accordance with their divine leadings is in that moment semi-divine.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Hicksite and liberal Friends accept textual criticism of the Bible and believe that, though inspired by God, the texts were nevertheless written and authored by humans with local concerns in various times and places.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures themselves are perhaps not alterable in the sense that the Biblical canon is relatively solidified, even for Quakers, but Friends have brought in outside texts to function as scriptures almost since their inception. Since scriptures are a secondary account of divine experience but not the experience itself, there can be numerous valid scriptural accounts.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Though pastors or committees might help each individual interpret the scriptures, the institutions themselves are not charged with interpreting the scriptures on behalf of the community. Depending on one's inclination, one might answer "no" as well.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Each individual is encouraged to interpret the scriptures for themselves.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Pastors and ministers in pastoral meetings. However, the Quaker process of scriptural interpretation is relatively decentralized.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: No. Beyond the Bible, insofar as there is a canon at all, it is informal and not codified.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: In the earliest days of Quakerism there was some debate over whether to build meetinghouses at all. Eventually structures were built, but only to be functional, in keeping with the Quaker testimony of simplicity. The Live Oak Friends Meetinghouse in Houston bears mentioning. Designed by James Turrell, the meetinghouse has a retractable roof designed to manipulate natural light in ways conducive to worship.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: One might think of the Friends as representing an anti-iconographic anti-ritual extreme on the Christian spectrum as they believe true worship occurs inwardly.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Although Friends believe any site could be sacred as the Light Within can be accessed anywhere, it would be accurate to say that meetinghouses are "dedicated to sacred practice" even if sacredness is not confined to their walls.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: In general no, though the Live Oak Friends Meeting pictured above constitutes an interesting exception.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The faculty that communes with the Inward Light is spiritual rather than material. Although Friends differ on the precise mode of divinity of that which receives the Light, it is never equated with the body. Indeed, Light is sometimes differentiated from mere conscience by Friends who draw such a distinction on this basis.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Many late nineteenth-century Friends were active in spiritualist movements in which the mind was understood to be able to manipulate physical matter. In traditional Quakerism, the notion that "Christ is spirit and must be worshipped in spirit" was taken rather literally.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The earliest Friends expected Christ's physical return imminently. Later Friends tended to internalize the second coming and emphasized doctrines of heaven and hell less than most Christians. Hicksite Friends disavowed hell almost entirely while Orthodox Friends adopted a similar eschatology and concept of afterlife to other Protestant Christians.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The term "afterlife" is somewhat misleading, as the Friends spoke less of a posthumous heaven and hell than did most Christian groups, though there are allusions to heaven. Rather, the world was seen as perfectible and so Friends imagined the "New Earth" in Revelation to reference a perfected version of the current world.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Notes: See above.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: A transcendent space.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: However, Friends were/are relatively lacking in funerary rituals when compared with other Christian groups.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Friends would sometimes choose to be buried in fields or away from formal cemeteries in keeping with their rejection of "separated" places as all places were potentially holy.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps not in the plural. The early Friends believed in a God who reveals himself to individuals through an Inward Light, but argued against the Trinity as non- or extra-Biblical. Modern conservative

Friends have adopted a more orthodox trinitarian theology. In general, other traditionally Christian supernatural beings like angels and demons have played a somewhat less important role in Quakerism than in other Christian and especially Catholic traditions. Though there are examples of Fox casting out demons, the discourse disappears from Quakerism after its more charismatic first two decades. A notable exception occurred in the spiritualist movement in late-nineteenth-century America and in Friends' mission work in areas where such beings were already taken as givens, such as Kenya and Bolivia.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Seventeenth-century Friends took the Protestant rejection of outward sacraments to one of its most extreme forms—some were internalized (e.g. communion) while many were rejected as unbiblical (e.g. water baptism). The Quaker God was startlingly nonanthropomorphic even by Protestant standards. Early Friends were non-creedal in addition to being nonsacramental and rejected trinitarian theology as unbiblical. Though some Friends continued to speak in God in similar turns, Quaker discussions of experience of the “Light Within” were far more common than discussions of God the Father or an even vaguely anthropomorphic creator god. Barclay and Fox were often charged with failing to differentiate the Light Within or Inward Light from mere conscience. Though the common Quaker defense was that the former was divine while conscience was a useful but “creaturely” faculty, the Friends struggled to make the differentiation intelligible to critics and sometimes even among themselves. Later Hicksite Friends made the identification explicit, and today many FGC Friends don't identify as theistic at all. The Gurneyite/FUM God is more anthropomorphic and personal in the evangelical sense.

Reference: Ingle, Homer Larry. *Quakers in Conflict*, 1998.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Quakers_in_Conflict.html?hl=&id=fCOJAAAACAAJ.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: In keeping with orthodox Christian understandings of God, the Quaker God is immanent and ontologically responsible for supporting all existence but is not tied to any one particular physical feature.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the god is a being at all.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
Notes: I suppose technically, though I have never seen a Friend stress this.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: Some conservative Friends would say yes but this has not been traditionally stressed in the Quaker tradition. More important is how each Friend responds to the Inward/Inner Light.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
Notes: Fox would sometimes pray for his enemies to be punished (and God acquiesced according to the Journal), as did individual Friends in later centuries. However, this has not been stressed in most versions of Quakerism.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Maybe more like "ineffectual" than impermissible. FGC Friends would say the Inner Light might be accessible through a variety of religious symbols, while many FUM Friends would counter that Christ-language is required.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: One might think of Quaker worship as a process of discernment by which one understands the voice of the Light Within.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Some late nineteenth spiritualists would say god speaks through both dreams and trances (and were even instrumental in formulating the concept of "trance") but this is a minority view in the tradition.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Some late nineteenth spiritualists would say god speaks through both dreams and trances (and were even instrumental in formulating the concept of "trance") but this is a minority view in the tradition.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Friends famously banned "hireling" or paid ministers. There is an old Quaker joke that rather than abolish the clergy the Quakers abolished the laity.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through worship

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that Friends have "that of god in them" and divine leadings can be accessed even in this life and world.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In some respects, the question of "supernatural monitoring" speaks to questions of sin, atonement, and divine intervention within the tradition. In early Quakerism and even throughout its Quietist period, God was seen as in charge of worldly affairs, sometimes indirectly (the gentle leadings of the Inward Light), sometimes directly—i.e. killing persecutors of the Quakers or answering the prayers of Friends in a direct way. Both themes recur in Quaker preaching as well as the journals and letters of individual Friends. However, Quaker atonement was downplayed compared to other traditions. The Light though immanently accessible and supernaturally endowed, did not monitor human behavior as would Santa Claus or Yama, rather, one would know one had acted sinfully if one's actions did not accord with divine leadings. In this sense, "sin" and its consequences arose from disobedience rather than an ontological condition. Friends rejected original sin and often charged Anglican ministers with using "sin" to prevent people from realizing their own potential perfection by turning toward the Light. This is relevant to the following list in the sense that one might say the Light "cares" about laziness, but not in a way that a Quaker will be "punished" for being lazy. Rather, having acted lazily, a Friend who queries the Inward Light will find they are spiritually unfulfilled partially on account of their laziness. The same is true with respect to many of the other categories. Hicksite Friends extended this argument to argue that Jesus was not ontologically significant and his blood was not required in any sacrifice since there was no debt to be repaid. Gurneyite Friends followed the evangelical line in affirming the importance of the historical Jesus who came to earth as the sole Son of God to redeem the world.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Friends were famous for erecting a "hedge" against the outside world. Those within received a great deal of spiritual and financial support (e.g. caretaking in times of need, mutual aid) but had to act in accordance with the strictures of the Society. Those who violated certain norms could be "disowned" or formally disavowed as a member of the community, even as they were often allowed to continue to participate in many of the community's functions, e.g. Meeting for Worship.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The Friends were anti-sacramental and so believed that while anywhere could potentially be a sacred place (an open field, a barn, and, presumably, even a Catholic cathedral), sacramental images inhibited worshipers' ability to query the Light Within.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

Notes: See perhaps the above answer on sacraments but nothing obvious comes to mind.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Notes: The only being is arguably the Light Within. Even Friends who speak of different forms of God (e.g. Light, Christ, Spirit, etc.) rarely speak about them in such a distinct way that they could be characterized as "caring" about each other.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Friends, as part of their "peace testimony" were near total pacifists, and believed all forms of warfare were morally wrong.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Friends could be disowned for adultery.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Friends could be disowned for incest (including first cousins).

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Friends could be disowned for any sex out of wedlock, though this was not always strictly enforced.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: This is an especially tricky query with respect to Quakers, who went to jail rather than swear oaths in a court of law. Since this shows the seriousness with which Quakers interpreted Jesus' injunction not to swear, I believe that constitutes a form of "honoring."

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, since fighting is motivated by the same spirit that motivates warfare. I imagine fighting for sport would constitute a gray area for many early Friends.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

Notes: The Quakers are formally anti-ritual, so I have checked "no." One might argue that certain Quaker practices (e.g. Meeting for Worship) actually constitute rituals insofar as they adhere to certain scholarly criteria, despite the Quaker disavowal. Under such a definition, the supernatural beings would care about ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

Notes: See above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: The early Friends sent missionaries all throughout England and even globally insofar as their resources permitted. The Quakers believed access to the Inward Light was universal and that non-religionists only needed to be taught how to discern the Light for themselves and would convert naturally.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The Friends famously introduced fixed-prices to England as they believed bargaining represented a form of dishonesty. In doing so they gained a reputation for honesty, priming their future business interests. Once they were more established, particularly in prosperous colonies like Pennsylvania, Friends came to believe that economic wealth often corresponded to hard work and virtue, but nevertheless took care of the poor, particularly within the Society, in keeping with the Biblical injunction.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Fox sometimes calls on God to punish his enemies, which God promptly does. However, Friends stress hell and the punishment of sinning far less than other Christian groups.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: To the Friends, although perhaps not to the one being punished.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: This is a possible reading of the examples in which God punishes those persecuting Friends.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Friends believed god acted on their behalf when petitioned, and on occasion even expressed remorse for those petitions.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Though I am inclined to say no. Some Orthodox Friends and certainly believe in a

traditionally Christian hell but the majority of the Quaker tradition has deemphasized or even eliminated the doctrine. The answers described in the subsection refer exclusively to the beliefs of those conservative Friends.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: As in the examples given above. However these are deemphasized and relatively rare.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: It could but deemphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: It could but deemphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: It could but deemphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: It could but deemphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: It could but deemphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: As above, Quakers deemphasize a physical heaven in favor of the perfected life one can live in this existence.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: One might argue this sociologically but within the tradition God doesn't explicitly grant rewards to enforce group norms.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Or, more often, through a process of discernment one would discover that one was acting selfishly and desire to change such that one's actions were in accord with divine leadings.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Although Friends speak on this far less often than other Christian groups, and afterlife discourse disappears almost entirely from Hicksite / FGC traditions.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Although this is more of an inference than something stressed within the tradition.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: If "eternal" is broadly conceived to include atemporal states of experience.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In the capacity of the spiritual benefits of turning toward the Inward Light.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of both inner peace and a society functioning in concert with one another and divine will.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The most important reward is living in accordance with the divine will itself.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Some early Friends in the 1650s and 1660s believed Jesus' arrival was immanent and had a very messianic eschatology. Some even seemed to believe that the Lamb's War, today often interpreted as an individual and social quest toward greater holiness, was a literal battle that would be fought on Earth. However, these beliefs had died down by the 1670s and 1680s and today do not play a major role in the tradition.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: For Fox and other early Friends, the second coming was spiritualized and internalized, such that anyone who turned toward the Light Within had experienced a messianic return. A more robust articulation of a physical second coming wouldn't occur until the pre-millennialist turn by evangelically-influenced Quakers in the late nineteenth-century.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Though Quaker uses of the "Inward Light" or "Light Within" in the seventeenth century were often confused and contradictory, the Light was almost always equated with the Christ in some sense, which in turn was sometimes treated as a principal but more often associated in some capacity with the historical Jesus.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the Light is available and realizable to all in this lifetime.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: Yes and no--early Friends believed the Coming was occurring by virtue of their very spiritual movement. Nevertheless, they understood that movement as the fulfillment of the early church and the initial disciples of Jesus.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the earliest Friends believed that they themselves had the same access to God as did Jesus, and in that sense could be considered messiahs themselves. And indeed, Friends were often charged under blasphemy laws for making claims of precisely this nature, for instance James Nayler's notorious "triumphal entry" into Bristol in 1656. The negative publicity associated with the blasphemy trial caused Friends to moderate some of their more extreme social and theological tendencies.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: As in traditional Christianity, Jesus' purpose in the Second Coming is to redeem the world from sin. However, Quakers famously spiritualized "The Lamb's War" described in Revelation as an internal struggle to be won through obedience and stressed the possibility of human redemption and perfection in this lifetime above the sinful consequences of nonbelievers. Indeed, the Friends thought the demons and satanic forces described in Revelation were metaphors describing the institutionalized Anglican church in their own day, not non-Christians, who Friends also believed had access to the Light Within.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: This is possible within the world as long as the community is sanctified. See for instance the quasi-theocratic government in Pennsylvania in which the members of the General Assembly rejected the governance of Penn and his chosen lieutenants in favor of one that operated according to discerning the will of the Light Within.

Reference: Calvert, Jane E.. *Quaker Constitutionalism and the Political Thought of John Dickinson*. Cambridge University Press, 2009.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Quaker_Constitutionalism_and_the_Politic.html?hl=&id=sTQ1AEVU_i0C.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Namely, the entire world would begin to operate in accordance with existent Quaker principles. The Quakers believed this would be accomplished through obedience to the leadings of the Light Within rather than through a divine war.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Though there is evidence that the 1650s Friends were an apocalyptic sect who believed the Second Coming was imminent, the Quakers quickly internalized the notion such that a "coming" occurred each time a Friend turned to the Light Within. Douglas Gwyn has argued that Fox embodied a "realized eschatology" in which the present world is the site of an eschatological transformation that has not yet been fully realized. In the Quietist period that followed, the Quakers shifted from a movement who thought God was using them to transform history into an institution whose purity would allow them to create a divinely-led just society within a sinful world. In the nineteenth century, Gurneyite Friends embraced pre-millennialism while eschatological discourse, conventionally understood, disappeared from liberal Quaker circles almost entirely.

Reference: Gwyn, Douglas. "Quakers, Eschatology, and Time". In *The Oxford Handbook of Quaker Studies*, edited by Stephen W. Angell and Pink Dandelion. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013.

Reference: Bruyneel, Sally. Margaret Fell and the End of Time, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Margaret_Fell_and_the_End_of_Time.html?hl=&id=A1YPgAACAAJ.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See the discussion of "realized eschatology" above. The eschaton can be accomplished by anyone who obeys their divine Light Within.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

Notes: With the qualification that many early Friends hoped the entire world would eventually convert to Quakerism, thereby realizing an eschaton through mass sanctification.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: See above, though Friends often spoke of realizing such a conversion within lifetimes rather than millenniums.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: Friends needed to obey the leadings of the Light Within, thereby allowing Christ to enact a Second Coming through the actions of those who obey his commands in the world.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but in the sense of patiently discerning the quiet leadings of the Light Within rather than a dramatic separation of the sheep from the goats coupled with a wrathful dispensation of judgment.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: Friends believed that their own communities had already been sanctified or at least created the conditions for sanctification. They hoped that a similar process would eventually

occur in the world at large.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: Though this is rarely stressed relative to the act of sanctification itself.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: Namely that the Quakers' own internal decision-making processes that are based on a shared sense of divine leadings would come to replace temporal governments based on kingship or the will of a simple majority.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: Quakerism itself would endure as the "universal" religious system.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as they follow their own Inward Light. In this sense, "survive" is not necessarily a binary condition.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Implicit in all surviving.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Though the sample region is irrelevant here.

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Yes. Put differently, the way one "dies" is by not following the leadings of the Light Within, not by being cast into hell.

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Friends have famously prescribed a number of social norms to sequester themselves from larger society in hopes of cultivating greater spiritual purity and discipline. Some of these practices include: Wearing plain dress ("Quaker gray"), a refusal to swear oaths, the exclusive use of the informal "thee", a refusal to remove one's hat in anyone's presence but the Lord's, fixed prices in trading, etc.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is an interesting question. I am tempted to say "yes" as Friends believed that all peoples possessed some knowledge of the divine even if they lacked knowledge of Christ or Christian language. However, within America and England, Friends were quite strict in enforcing their own social practices and were quick to disown or chastise those who violated them.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: Namely the Inward/Inner Light.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Notes: Same as above, the Inward Light.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: Depending on how one defines the Christian god, but the Quaker articulation of god is famously non-anthropomorphic.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Notes: One can only expect those acquainted with the moral norms to act on them, but in principal they would be knowable and realizable by any individual at any time.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in both the spiritual and ethical senses. Quaker meetings were historically “unprogrammed” in favor of radical openness to the Spirit and its Leadings. As such, a central virtue was the ability to discern the will of the Light Within and communicate it to others without interjecting one’s own desires or ideals into the discernment process. Similarly, as Quaker worship became increasingly quietist and foregrounded active listening during meeting for worship, patience emerged as another central virtue. Since Quaker meeting for business and other committees generally take the form of worship with a goal of divine openness rather than to achieve specific policy or organizational goals, clerks and other Friends who were skilled in listening and dialogue became especially valued. Though Quaker worship was decidedly inwardly-oriented, Rufus Jones formalized a longstanding Quaker belief in arguing that the most convincing inner experience was a life of service to others. The reason the Quakers have drawn such significant scholarly and popular attention despite their relatively small population is due to their disproportionate influence in progressive social causes—abolitionism, women’s rights, Native American rights, educational reform, environmentalism, and mental health reform are all causes that were founded or significantly influenced by Friends. A formulation of Quaker “testimonies” or values popular today in Quaker colleges and secondary schools is the SPICES acronym: simplicity, peace, integrity, community, equality, and stewardship.

Reference: Frost, J. W., ed.. *The Quaker Origins of Antislavery*. Edited by J. W. Frost. Norwood: Norwood Editions, 1980.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: The Quaker refusal to take oaths stems from their understanding of a Biblical injunction against swearing as one’s word should always be truthful. A number of Quaker anecdotes revolve around Friends trying to avoid lying while nevertheless preserving their other ethical commitments. For example, Levi Coffin, a “conductor” on the Underground Railroad was secretly transporting slaves north in a wagon with a false bottom covered with vases and straw. When a slave catcher asked what Coffin was transporting, he answered, “earthen vessels” in an attempt to dissemble rather than lie outright.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: "Tolerance" is a distinctly Quaker value. One reason early Friends were charged with blasphemy was their assertion that all people everywhere had equal access to divine truth, whether they had realized it or not.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

Notes: Though Quakers sought to sequester themselves from larger society in order to preserve their moral purity, they rejected rituals as sacramental and had little concern with ritual purity.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: On balance these are Quaker values, though the early Friends were famous for disrupting public events (including other church services) to preach and for refusing to doff their hats for anyone but God.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: The Quaker process of divine listening often involved discerning and interpreting gentle nudges over the course of years and years, leading to patience emerging as a particularly important value within Quakerism.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: So long as these terms are spiritually interpreted. Friends were also famous for their dour manner and rejection of most worldly pleasures (music, dancing, reading for pleasure, etc.).

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Divine discernment in particular above ordinary intelligence. The two were sometimes but connected but Friends also saw such receptivity as a spiritual gift in its own right.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No, although the Shakers, who famously require such celibacy, were originally known as the "Shaking Quakers" and were an offshoot of the Society.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: George Fox and the early Friends mixed preaching to be in control of one's passions and to abstain from sexual perversions with highly affectionate modes of address (e.g. quoting the Song of Songs at length in letters and addresses) and greetings that often led to Friends being charged with sexual perversion themselves. As Friends transitioned into a less charismatic Quietist period, they continued to warn against lust and any loss of control over one's faculties. Friends could be disowned for sex outside of marriage, incest, and adultery, but in this Friends were decidedly within the English and American mainstreams. Sexuality did not become a significant issue within the Society until the rise of the LGBT movement in the 1960s and 70s. Meetings affiliated with Friends United Meeting toed the evangelical line in refusing to hire any openly-gay noncelibate officials or perform any gay weddings. This then would be a form of abstinence, insofar as some meetings allow members to identify as gay or lesbian in orientation but not to act sexually on those urges. More liberal FGC Friends have followed the liberal edge of American politics more generally, and today many affirm LGBT relationships of all kinds, framing the issue as continuing the Quakers' championing of underprivileged groups throughout history.

Reference: Doan, Petra L., and Elizabeth P. Kamphausen. "Quakers and Sexuality". In *The Oxford Handbook of Quaker Studies*, edited by Stephen W. Angell and Pink Dandelion. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013.

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: The Friends, in keeping with other Christian groups, traditionally advocated for marriage between a man and a woman, who were then only permitted to have sex with one another. Sex was not permitted outside of a conjugal relationship.

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: The Friends, in keeping with other Christian groups, traditionally advocated for marriage between a man and a woman, who were then only permitted to have sex with one another. Sex was not permitted outside of a conjugal relationship.

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Sex was not permitted outside of marriage and warnings against lust and licentiousness were common.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Sex was not permitted outside of marriage and warnings against lust and licentiousness were common.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is considered a spiritual discipline that individual Quakers are welcome to practice. However, it has never been required for membership in the Society.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: At least weekly attendance at Meetings for Worship. Since Quakers lack a priesthood or ministerial hierarchy, they are responsible for their own governance and must also give up considerable time to meetings devoted to managing the affairs of the Society.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Not officially, as Quakers are anti-creedal, but all Friends would agree that ethical precepts should be discerned and followed.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Although one might argue certain Quaker practices are in fact rituals over Quaker objections, Friends carry the Protestant anti-ritual impulse to an extreme.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: In the past plain dress would have applied, but the practice has largely been forsaken over the last century.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although in varying forms. FUM Friends have adopted the more common evangelical

parlance of referring to one another as “brothers and sisters in Christ.” There are references to earlier Friends speaking of the entire world as a single family and some have argued that this was in hopes that the Quakers own family model would become an exemplar for the entire world. Due to the practice of endogamy until the mid-nineteenth century, some have argued that Friends quite literally came to see themselves as a family both spiritually and physically set apart.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: Or, common but only among evangelical Friends.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A society, denomination, or movement

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The American Friends Service Committee and the British Friends Service Council were two of the only aid organizations permitted to operate in Germany following each of the world wars and were instrumental in feeding its civilian population. The two organizations were jointly awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 1947 for their efforts.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: I suppose through their respective national governments.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Primarily through the AFSC. Local meetings have also historically taken care of destitute members in their own meeting.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Respective national governments.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: At different points in their history, but relatively decentralized.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Respective national governments.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Religious education is often conducted by the meeting in First Day Classes or other weekly groups. The Friends are also famous for their secondary schools, e.g. Sidwell Friends in D.C. which is home to the children of a number of Washington dignitaries. There are also a number of Quaker colleges, including Bryn Mawr College, Earlham College, Guilford College, Haverford College, Swarthmore College, and George Fox University. The Woodbrooke Quaker Study Centre in Birmingham, England also bears mentioning.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Government schools, other private schools.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Quaker system of internal governance is relatively complicated. Each local meeting belongs to a subgroup of meetings, culminating in a "Yearly Meeting." The yearly meetings themselves belong to either the FGC or the FUM (described above) or one of the smaller Quaker associations. (E.g. FGC is currently comprised of 16 yearly meetings and 10 monthly meetings.) See, for example, the British Friends' organizational structure here: <https://www.quaker.org.uk/our-organisation/our-structures>.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, relevant governmental bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Quakers from their inception have been opposed to compulsory tithing as they did not understand tithes to be a Biblical injunction. However, Friends have always donated funds for the maintenance of the Society.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: National and state governments.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Although weighty Friends might be asked to intercede or judge disputes within members of the Society.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Friends can be disowned from their meetings, but there is no further punishment.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the U.S. government continues to execute people.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Some Friends refuse to pay taxes, or portions of their taxes, on grounds that their tax dollars support wars. On occasion the IRS seizes their funds directly.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Quakers are pacifists who oppose war, military service, and the draft. The question of how to live out the peace testimony during times of a national draft has been a crucial one throughout Quaker history. Some Friends have gone to jail, others have fled to foreign countries, while others worked in "alternative service" projects that were often funded and overseen by the meetings themselves.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: That of the country in which they reside.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Friends basically use the same calendar but refer to it by their own names (e.g. First Day for Sunday) so as to avoid pagan associations.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above but it basically corresponds to the Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The capitalist infrastructure

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